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NATIONAL VALUES AND CONFLICTS WITH MASS CULTURE: PRESERVING HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL HERITAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the importance of preserving Uzbekistan's rich historical and cultural heritage from the perspective of conflicts between national values and mass culture. The centuries-old historical and cultural wealth of Uzbekistan plays a crucial role not only in preserving national identity but also in enhancing the country's reputation on the international stage. The article examines measures in the fields of education, tourism, and legislation for preserving national values. Additionally, it highlights the importance of international cooperation in the restoration and preservation of historical monuments. Through this analysis, the necessary steps to transmit historical and cultural heritage to future generations are presented.

Keywords: Historical heritage, cultural heritage, national values, mass culture, preservation, restoration

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, the process of globalization, the spread of mass culture through mass media and the internet significantly impact national values and cultural heritage. Uzbekistan is one of the countries with a rich historical and cultural heritage, which forms the foundation of the people's national values and traditions. Preserving and transmitting this heritage to future generations is one of the crucial tasks. Protecting historical and cultural heritage is important not only for maintaining the national identity but also for enhancing the country's international prestige. This situation leads to conflicts between national values and mass culture. This article explores the issues of preserving national values and protecting them from the invasion of mass culture.

National Values and Their Importance

National values are the spiritual and cultural heritage of every people. They include customs, traditions, national costumes, folk music, cultural heritage objects, and many other elements. National values play an essential role in

preserving the uniqueness of the people and transmitting their historical heritage to future generations.

Mass Culture and Its Impact

Mass culture represents ideas, cultural elements, and lifestyles spread mainly through mass media and the internet. Due to its rapid and widespread dissemination, this culture negatively affects the cultural heritage and values of various nations. Often, mass culture leads to the loss of national values and the introduction of global cultural elements.

Figure 1. Conflict between National Values and Mass Culture

Importance of Preserving Historical and Cultural Heritage

Historical and cultural heritage are unique treasures left from the nation's past. They are significant not only for the people but also for the world's culture. Preserving historical heritage objects and transmitting them to future generations is one of the crucial tasks. To accomplish this, the state and society must undertake several measures.

Methods for Preserving National Values and Counteracting Mass Culture

To preserve national values and protect them from the invasion of mass culture, the following measures can be implemented:

1. Education and upbringing: Focus on national history, culture, and traditions in educational systems to instill national values in the younger generation.
2. Mass media: Promote national culture and prepare materials counteracting mass culture to protect national values.
3. Cultural events: Widely promote national values among the people through national holidays, festivals, and cultural events.
4. Legislation: Develop and ensure the implementation of laws and regulations aimed at protecting national cultural heritage.

1. Historical and Cultural Heritage of Uzbekistan

Uzbekistan's territory is rich in cultural and archaeological monuments from various historical periods. Among these are ancient architectural monuments in cities like Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva, archaeological excavations in the Amu Darya and Syr Darya valleys, and rich folk oral traditions and customs.

2. Importance of Preserving Historical and Cultural Heritage

Preserving Uzbekistan's historical and cultural heritage has several important aspects:

1. Maintaining national identity: Historical and cultural heritage is a key factor in preserving the people's identity and national values. Losing this heritage can lead to the loss of the nation's historical memory.

2. Tourism development: Historical and cultural monuments contribute to the development of tourism. Uzbekistan's rich heritage plays an important role in attracting foreign tourists, which benefits the country's economy.

3. Education and upbringing: Historical and cultural heritage plays a significant role in educating the younger generation. Through this heritage, young people can learn about national values, history, and culture.

4. International relations: Uzbekistan's rich historical and cultural heritage enhances the country's international reputation and promotes cultural cooperation with other countries.

Conclusion

Preserving Uzbekistan's rich historical and cultural heritage is one of the important tasks facing the state and society. Protecting this heritage not only preserves national values and historical memory but also contributes to the country's economic and international development. Therefore, all necessary measures must be taken to protect historical and cultural heritage.

Measures for Preserving Historical and Cultural Heritage

Uzbekistan must implement several measures to preserve its historical and cultural heritage:

1. Legislation and policy: Develop and implement laws and regulations aimed at protecting historical and cultural heritage. Strengthen the activities of state bodies in this regard.

2. Education and promotion: Focus on studying historical and cultural heritage in the education system and nurture respect for national values and heritage among the youth.

3. Restoration and conservation: Attract necessary financial and technical resources for the restoration and conservation of historical monuments.

4. International cooperation: Develop cooperation with international organizations and foreign countries, exchange experiences in the field of cultural heritage protection.

References:

1. Abdujabborov, A. (2020). History of Uzbekistan. Tashkent: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan.

2. Karimov, I. (1999). Uzbekistan: National Independence, Economy, Politics, Ideology. Tashkent: Uzbekistan.

3. Rasulov, M. (2017). "Current Issues of Cultural Heritage Protection in Uzbekistan". Journal of Culture and Art, No. 4, pp. 45-57.

4. Qosimov, T. (2015). Cultural Heritage of Uzbekistan: History and Prospects. Tashkent: Shorq.

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5. UNESCO. (2021). "Uzbekistan — Intangible Cultural Heritage". Retrieved from the UNESCO website.
6. Sodiqova, N. (2018). "Customs and Traditions of the Uzbek People". Journal of Uzbek Culture and History, No. 3, pp. 30-44.
7. Ismoilov, D. (2022). "Preservation and Restoration of Historical Monuments in Uzbekistan". Journal of Architecture and Ancient Monuments, No. 2, pp. 78-85.
8. Ministry of Tourism and Culture. (2023). Development of Tourism and Cultural Heritage in Uzbekistan. Tashkent: Ministry of Tourism and Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
9. Safarov, K. (2019). Archaeological Heritage of Uzbekistan. Tashkent: Fan.
10. Mahmudov, A. (2016). "National Values and Their Role in the Education of Youth". Journal of Education and Upbringing, No. 1, pp. 23-35.